

Composition and Abundance of Plant Parasitic Nematodes of Some Important Food Crops in Abuja FCT

¹Anih Agatha C., ²Ndana, R.W., ³Okwute S. K., ⁴Anjorin, S.T.

¹Biological Science Department, Faculty of Science, Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano, ²Department of Biology, University of Abuja FCT Abuja, ³Department of Chemistry, University of Abuja, ⁴Department of Crop Protection, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Abuja

Abstract-: The survey carried out was to assess the composition and abundance of plant parasitic nematodes that exist in Abuja-Nigeria. This is in view of identifying the different types of plant parasitic nematodes that exist and cause low yield of crops in the FCT- Abuja in Nigeria. Soil and root samples collected from the rhizospheres from different farmland of the six Municipal Area Councils of FCT were analyzed by carrying out nematodes' extraction targeting the different stages of plant parasitic nematodes, identification of the isolated nematodes and the quantification using different standard methods. The results showed that seven genera of plant parasitic nematodes which include *Meloidogyne*, *Pratylenchus*, *Scutellonema*, *Ditylenchus*, *Helicotylenchus*, *Aphelenchus*, and *Criconemoides* identified across the 180 composite samples from both plant and root sampled from the different community sites in Federal Capital Territory Abuja. *Meloidogyne* (34.4%), *Helicotylenchus* (27.39%), *Scutellonema* (11.59%), *Ditylenchus* (9.90%), *Pratylenchus* (6.79%), *Aphelenchus* (4.93%), and *Criconemoides* (4.93%) were the most prevalent generic plant parasitic nematodes found in FCT-Abuja. Kuje area council was found to have the highest frequency of nematode infestation (29.19%), followed by Kwali (15.81%), Abaji, AMAC, and Gwagwalada recording a frequency of (14.27-15.91%), and AMAC area council with a frequency of 9.41%

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1.0 Introduction

A major challenge facing agricultural scientists today is the need to secure food for an increasing world population which is projected to 35% increase by 2050 (FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO, 2017). The increasing population suggests an increase in food demand that is estimated to be of about 75% due to economic development and changes in food preferences (Bajželj *et al.*, 2014).

Food crops are being affected by various groups of plant parasitic nematodes, which exist wherever plants grow in every corner of the world with an incredible diversity. They are known to be among the constraints of producing food for man and livestock. It causes significant damage to almost all crops. The annual worldwide losses caused by nematodes on the life sustaining crops, which include all kinds of food crops are estimated to be about 11% and losses for most other economically important crops are about 14% for a total of over \$ 80 billion annually (Coyne and Affokpon, 2018).

One basic feature of nematode attack, however, is that nutrient and metabolic activities are diverted from normal healthy growth and fruit production and repairing the wounds they cause is a chronic problem that continues throughout the growing season. Plant diseases are caused by individual nematode species or by a combination of several species or nematodes interacting with other pathogens to produce disease complexes which are produced by the interaction of nematodes with pathogenic bacteria or fungi are more damaging to plants than these pathogens acting alone. Nematodes have evolved various types of association with plants. The root-knot nematodes, due to their high reproductive potential and wide host ranges are notoriously difficult to manage. *Meloidogyne* requires 99.9% control to prevent the subsequent buildup of damaging populations (Chaudhary and Kaul, 2013). A diverse mixture of plant parasitic and free-living nematodes is present in most soil samples. These nematodes can be easily isolated from both soil and root samples for viewing and

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identification of the actual pathogen is essential for effective disease control (Stirling, 2018).

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2.0 Material and Method

2.1 Collection of soil and root sample

Soil and root samples were collected from the rhizosphere of the plants with the aid of a soil auger to a depth of about 15 cm and within a 25 cm radius from the base of each plant. Thirty soil core samples per hectare were randomly taken from each of the area council and bulked together to form a composite sample and the bulk passed over a 10 mm diameter mesh sieve to remove all stones and debris. The sieved soil packed in a sealed transparent polythene bag and properly labeled with attention given to the date of collection, time, location, and field from which the samples were collected. The crop samples that were uprooted were taken to the lab for nematode extraction. The shoot and the root of sampled crops had remarkably different colors where they were separated. The location where these samples were collected includes the six Area Councils of the Federal Capital Territory. From each of the fields, the following non-woody crops were sampled *Sorghum bicolor*, *Abelmoschus esculentus*, *Sesamum indicum*, *Ipomea batatas*, *Arachis hypogea*, *Lycopersicon esculentum*, *Vigna unguiculata*, *Solanum melongena*, *Manihot esculentum*, *Dioscorea rotundata* and *Glycine max* of peasant farmers.

2.2 Extraction, Sampling and Diagnosis of Plant Parasitic Nematodes from Soil and root samples

A subsample of soil (200g) and roots (10 g) were extracted, sieved, and decanted through a 40- μ m sieve, following Cobb (1918). This was followed by using a stack of sieves pore size (43, 250 μ m). Each soil sample was thoroughly mixed, and 200g of soil was drawn from the homogenous mixtures for processing. The 200g homogenous mixtures were placed in a plastic beaker containing 1000 ml of water to enable the soil sample properly suspend the suspension was stirred well and allowed to stand for 10 seconds. The muddy suspension was then passed through 20-mesh size sieve to discard stone and other coarse materials. The suspension from the first basket was collected in a second basket and allowed to settle for about 15-30 seconds and then passed through a 60-mesh size (250 μ m

pore) into third basket leaving the heavy particles in the sieve. The filtrate after settled for some time was passed through 350 mesh (43 μ m pore) sieve. Then, the quantity of water was reduced by decanting after allowing the nematodes to settle at the bottom. The suspension containing nematodes was then passed gently over a double-layered tissue paper placed over an aluminium mesh-supported Petri plate containing filtered water. Collected samples were placed following a Baermann funnel technique. In this method, the required 100 ml beaker of soil is rinsed through an 864 μ m sieve (17 mesh size) and over a 38 μ m sieve (392 mesh size). The filtered soil sample was rinsed into a coffee filter placed within funnel and supported by a screen. The water level is brought up to at least 1.0 cm above the coffee filter and allowed to incubate for 24 hours. Motile nematodes were extracted from soil solution.

The collected soil sample was homogenized gently by hand and stored in a plastic bag in an insulated container and nematodes extraction was done within 24 to 72 hours it was collected. For the root sample, it was kept in a perforated plastic bag. These samples were stored within a humid temperature of not more than 20 °C. The collected soil samples from the various fields/farms were brought to the laboratory for screening, which involves nematode extraction; this is in view of identifying and quantifying the different types of nematodes that exist in each area in relation to the type of crop that is being grown. For the extraction of nematode from the soil sample, two methods were employed to extract the plant parasitic nematodes for identification, and any of these methods is dependent on the type and the juvenile stage of nematode that is to be extracted. Sieve method and Modified Baermann funnel method was applied, in this, different stages of plant parasitic nematodes that inhabit the soil was targeted from each of the soil and root sample. For Sieve method, the soil sample was mixed thoroughly, to homogenize the nematodes within the soil. A 50 ml soil was measured and rinsed through an 864 μ m (20 meshes) sieve into a large pitcher. The filtrate was mixed with a pressurized water spray to fill the pitcher. After allowing the water and soil in the pitcher to settle for 20 seconds, the suspension was poured over a 38 μ m (400 meshes) sieve held at a 45° angle. Material captured on the sieve was rinsed into a 50 ml collection tube and was allowed to settle for 20

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minutes. The supernatant was poured over a 25 µm (500 meshes) sieve. The resulting material captured on the sieve was examined under a light microscope for identification and quantification of the nematode juveniles. Diagnostic sampling also included root samples or visual assessments. Collected samples were placed following a modified Baermann funnel. In this method, the required volume of soil is rinsed through an 864 µm sieve and over a 38 µm sieve. The captured material was rinsed into a coffee filter placed within funnel and supported by a screen. The water level is brought up to at least 1.0 cm above the coffee filter and allowed to incubate for 24 hours. Following incubation, the filter and screen are removed from the bowl and the water left in the bowl or funnel base is poured over a 25 µm sieve. Motile nematodes were extracted from soil. A prepared slide of this was viewed under a digital microscope with magnification of X4 objective with X10 eye piece, (X40). Plant parasitic nematode was identified using the head, body shape and stylet morphology. The nematode extracts also were identified and quantified using a standard identification key with help of pictorial key to genera of plant parasitic nematodes (Mai and Lyon 1975), and an identification key for agriculturally important plant-parasitic nematode according to Tesfamariam, Mekete *et al.*, (2012) and the count was also recorded

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Abundance and composition of Plant parasitic nematodes (PPN) isolated from Federal Capital Territory

A total of 180 composite soil and root samples were collected from fields in seven area councils of FCT Abuja to identify the composition and abundance of plant parasitic nematodes. Seven genera of PPN were found, with *Meloidogyne* being the most prevalent (34.49%), followed by *Helicotylenchus* (27.39%), *Scutellonema* (11.59%), *Ditylenchus* (9.90%), *Pratylenchus* (6.79%), *Aphelenchus* (4.93%) and *Criconemoides* (4.91%). These genera have been known to cause significant damage to crops. The percentage next to each genus shows its proportion relative to the total number of survey sites where they were detected. Table 1 shows the frequency rating of plant parasitic nematodes isolated from the field. Kuje area council was found to have the highest frequency of nematode infestation (29.19%), this was followed by

Gwagwalada (15.91%), Kwali (15.81%), Bwari (15.39%). Abaji (14.27%) while AMAC had the least percentage of occurrence (9.41%).

3.2 Occurrence and Distribution of Plant Parasitic Nematodes on food crops in FCT-ABUJA.

Plant parasitic nematodes were isolated from different crops that are being grown in FCT-Abuja. The abundance and distribution of the isolated PPN. Results in Table 2 showed that vegetable crops like *Lycoperscium esculentus* and *Abelmoschus esculentus* were highly attacked by *Meloidogyne species*. This is followed by *Helicotylenchus*, which is also found to be more abundant and followed by *Scutellonema*. All the other plant parasitic nematodes were found at different degrees of abundance in the different crops that were sampled.

4.0 Conclusion

The results of tables 1 and 2 above showed that *Meloidogyne* (root-knot nematode) and *Helicotylenchus* are the most common Plant parasitic nematodes found in all the six Area Councils of FCT Abuja. This is also found to attack the most widely consumed crop as both food and a source of economy for livelihood for the indigenous farmers in FCT- Abuja. Kuje Area Council is found to have the highest population of plant parasitic nematodes attacking different crops (Other area councils also recorded a high prevalence of Plant-parasitic nematodes, according to the scale by Sasser and Taylor in 1984, there is the high susceptibility of plant parasitic nematodes in the Agricultural system in Federal Capital Territory.

Figures and Tables

Table 1: Numbers (N) and Percentage of Plant Parasitic Nematodes (Genera) Present in 200 Cm³ Soil Samples from Federal Capital Territory, Abuja

Nematode genera	Abaji		AMAC		Bwari		Gwagwalada		Kuje		Kwali		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
<i>Meloidogyne</i>	4760	18.39	2340	9.03	2650	10.24	5760	22.25	8510	32.87	1870	7.22	25890	34.49
<i>Helicotylenchus</i>	2300	38.65	1500	31.71	3100	34.83	2560	41.36	7100	52.95	4000	40	20560	27.39
<i>Scutellonema</i>	1600	26.88	700	14.78	3500	39.33	900	14.54	900	6.71	1100	11	8700	11.59
<i>Ditylenchus</i>	0	0	950	20.09	1100	12.36	880	14.22	1800	13.42	2700	27	7430	9.90
<i>Pratylenchus</i>	1150	19.33	600	12.69	800	8.99	550	8.89	100	0.75	1900	19	5100	6.79
<i>Aphelenchus</i>	800	13.45	800	16.92	300	3.37	1200	19.39	600	4.48	0	0	3700	4.93
<i>Criconemoides</i>	100	1.68	180	3.81	100	1.13	100	1.62	2910	21.7	300	3	3690	4.91
Total percentage*		14.27		9.41		15.39		15.91		29.19		15.81	75070	100

N= Number of PPN isolates, % = the frequency of occurrence of ppn percentage

Table 2. Occurrence and Distribution of Plant parasitic nematodes on food crops in FCT-ABUJA

	<i>M</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>C</i>
<i>Sesamum indicum</i> Linn.	++	++	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Lycoperscium esculentus</i> Mill	+++	++	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Dioscorea rotundata</i> Linn.	++	++	++	+	+	+	+
<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i> Linn.	+++	+	-	++	+	+	+
<i>Ipomea batatas</i> Linn	+	+	++	+	++	+	+
<i>Solanum melongena</i> Linn	++	+	++	-	+	+	+
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> Linn.	++	++	+	-	++	-	+
<i>Manihot esculentus</i> Linn	++	++	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> Linn.Walp.	++	+	+	++	+	+	+
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i> Linn	++	++	-	+	-	++	+

Glycine max Linn.Merrill

+ - - - - - -

M- *Meloidogyne*, H- *Helicotylenchus*, S-*Scutellonema*, D- *Ditylenchus*, P-*Pratylenchus*, A-*Apelenchus*,
C- *Criconemoides*

= Absent, + = 1-100, ++ = 101-1000, +++ = 1001-10,000

Author Contribution

Authors contributed equally

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest is declared

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